

On Neutrosophy logic for Multiple Correlation Analysis in Fuzzy Uncertain Database

Samar Wazir^{1*}, M.M. Sufyan Beg², Tanvir Ahmad³, Shahab Saquib Sohail⁴

¹Department of Computer Engineering, Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi, India; samar.wazir786@gmail.com

²Department of Computer Engineering Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, India; mmsbeg@myamu.ac.in

³Department of Computer Engineering, Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi, India; tahmad2@jmi.ac.in

⁴ School of Computing Science and Engineering, VIT Bhopal University, Sehore, MP 466114, India; shahabsaquibsohail@vitbhopal.ac.in

* Correspondence: samar.wazir786@gmail.com, shahabsaquibsohail@vitbhopal.ac.in

Abstract: The primary goal of this paper is to introduce a novel method for mining frequent and interesting items by incorporating correlation analysis between two items in an uncertain transactional database using the OWA operator. The work is further expanded by proposing two additional methods for mining frequent and interesting items, utilizing fuzzy means and the OWA operator along with multiple correlation analysis for more than two items in uncertain transactional databases. The effectiveness of the proposed methods is evaluated by running the algorithms on both standard and example datasets, with results compared to the traditional probabilistic approach for identifying frequent and interesting items through multiple correlation. While multiple correlation analysis highlights the relationships of interestingness and uninterestingness between items, the OWA operator enhances the results when combined with fuzzy means and probabilistic methods. Additionally, the paper suggests a future research direction using Neutrosophy logic, which is anticipated to open new avenues for further exploration in this field.

Keywords: Frequent Itemset Mining; Minimum Support; Correlation Analysis; Certain/Uncertain Databases; Fuzzy Operators; Ordered Weighted Averaging; Neutrosophy logic; Neutrosophic cognitive map.

1. Introduction

Over the past two decades, the increasing reliance of industries on information technology has led to the generation of massive amounts of unstructured data. As a result, extracting relevant and useful information from this vast pool has become a complex and challenging task. Consequently, the challenge of mining valuable insights from large databases has emerged as a key area of study within computer science, commonly referred to as data mining [1].

The database used in this mining process, known as a transactional database, can be viewed as a collection of transactions (rows) and the items (values) within each transaction. The usefulness of the results generated by the data mining process is determined by several key parameters, such as the frequency of an item or itemset in the database (called support), the likelihood that the presence of one item is linked to the presence of another in the same itemset (called confidence), and the relationship between the occurrence of one item and the increased or decreased occurrence of others (called correlation) [1-2].

The process of extracting frequently occurring items or itemsets from a transactional database is known as Frequent Itemset Mining (FIM) [3], a sub-discipline of data mining and one of the most

active research fields. Numerous FIM algorithms [3-5] have been developed, which can be classified based on their execution pattern (i.e., sequential or parallel) or the type of database used (i.e., certain, probabilistic, or fuzzy). In a certain database, the support of an itemset is determined by its count in the database [6]. In a probabilistic database, support is based on the existential probability of the itemset [7-9], whereas in a fuzzy database, support is calculated using fuzzy operators such as min, max, or mean [10].

An item or itemset is considered frequent if its support meets or exceeds a user-specified minimum support threshold. For example, in Market Basket Analysis [11], if a database contains 100 transactions, and the item counts for milk and eggs are 20 and 30 respectively, and the minimum support is set to 30, then eggs would be classified as frequent, while milk would not. To enhance the mining process or improve item sales, not only is item count considered, but also whether the sale of one item (e.g., milk) influences the sale of another (e.g., eggs). This type of relationship between two or more items is called ****correlation****, and items that meet both the minimum support and correlation thresholds are deemed frequent and interesting.

Correlation between two items is often measured using the Correlation Coefficient [12]. In the case of Pearson’s Correlation Coefficient, values range between [-1, 1]. A value of 0 indicates that the two items are independent of each other, a positive value (between 0 and 1) indicates a positive dependence, and a negative value (between 0 and -1) indicates a negative dependence. Various algorithms have been developed to calculate correlations between two or more items in certain, probabilistic, and fuzzy uncertain databases.

Consider the Uncertain Database (UDB) shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Uncertain Database

TID	Milk	Eggs
1	0.9	0.01
2	0.01	0.03
3	0.03	0.23
4	0.06	0.15
5	0.05	0.3
6	0.08	0.89

In the above database, TID denotes transaction id; there are two items in the database, i.e., milk and eggs, the value of each item shows the existential probability or the membership function of the particular item in the transaction if the database is considered as probabilistic uncertain or fuzzy uncertain respectively. Therefore, if the correlation [13] between milk and eggs is calculated using probability or fuzzy means [14-17], then the following cases can be considered as given in table 2.

Table 2. Illustration of different possible cases in a database

Cases	Correlation using probability	Correlation using fuzzy means
✓ Case 1: No Change	-0.18454	-0.33829
✓ Case 2: TID2 is removed from the database	-0.25055	-0.47403
✓ Case 3: TID1 is removed from the database	0.058944	0.797699
✓ Case 4: TID1 & TID2 are removed	0.015756	0.593577

from the database

So, in case 1 milk and eggs are negatively correlated whereas, in Case 3 they are highly positively correlated. In the above database, it can be seen that only two high values (i.e., milk 0.9 and eggs 0.89) affects the whole correlation coefficient and ignores other small values, in fact, while calculating correlation the participation of all values should be considered so that the interesting relationship can be calculated. Another difference can be seen in case 3 and 4, where probabilistic values show fewer correlation compare to highly correlated values by fuzzy means. The difference is due to the multiplication of probabilistic values while calculating correlation.

The above analysis states that we need some better approach than probabilistic approach and fuzzy means, and also calculated correlation coefficient must lie between $[1, -1]$ (because in this paper Pearson's Correlation Coefficient is considered).

In this paper, the following contribution has been done

1. A new method has been proposed for calculating the correlation between two items using OWA (Ordered Weighted Averaging).
2. A proof is given to show that Correlation Coefficient between two items using OWA lies between -1 and 1.
3. A new method is proposed for calculating correlation among more than two items using fuzzy means, and frequent itemsets have been calculated with the help of this method, the algorithm named as MCAFM (*Multiple Correlation Analysis using Fuzzy Means*).
4. A new method is proposed for calculating correlation among more than two items using OWA, and frequent itemsets have been calculated with the help of this method, the algorithm named as MCAOWA (*Multiple Correlation Analysis using OWA*).
5. A proof is given to show that using OWA would be a better approach than using Fuzzy Means while calculating Correlation among two or more items.
6. The MCAFM and MCAOWA algorithms are presented and explained.
7. **Neutrosophy logic framework for pattern mining is suggested.**
8. Algorithms are executed on standard and synthetic datasets and results are compared with the traditional probabilistic approach.

2. Related works

The risk involved in the improvement or change of the current business scenario can only be resolved either by mathematical induction or by analyzing previously available data. Thereupon, as the demand for analyzing past data increased exponentially in the last decade, the field of FIM gained popularity. The applications of FIM [4] range from market basket analysis, crime analysis and prevention to software bug detection, DNA matching and image processing.

The first algorithm of FIM was proposed by Agarwal in 1994 as Apriori[6] algorithm for calculating frequent items on the certain transactional database (CTD) which is based on sequential execution pattern, and subsequently, the list of FIM algorithms have been increased dramatically, e.g. FPGrowth [18], ECLAT [19-21]. Apriori was unable to handle a large amount of data, henceforth, the need for parallel algorithms encounters and Count Distribution (CD) [7], [22] was developed. The step-by-step refinement in CD reflects in the development of Data Distribution (DD) [23], Fast Parallel Mining (FPM) [20] and Fast Distributed Mining (FDM)[19] algorithms.

In many applications where the generated data is uncertain/imprecise/unstructured, it is not justified to store this information as CTD, e.g., prediction of customer purchasing behaviour from

market basket data [24], data from GPS, data from RFID, data collected for predicting rain, temperature and humidity. Such kind of data is stored as probabilistic uncertain database (PUD), and in this database each item is associated with its existential probability, e.g., in Table 1 if we consider it as PUD and TID denotes customer number then it can be said that there is a 90% chance that customer 1 would purchase milk and 3% chance that customer 2 would purchase eggs. The first algorithm for calculating frequent items on PUD was developed by Chui [25-26], as UApriori which calculates frequent items based on expected support and follows Apriori execution pattern, e.g. expected the support of {milk, eggs} in Table 1 is 0.1114. After UApriori various algorithms were developed for FIM on PUD such as Poisson Distribution Based UApriori (PDU), Normal Distribution based UApriori(NDU) [27-29], UFGrowth [30], UECLAT [31] etc.

Uncertain algorithms are unable to calculate frequent items for large sizes (e.g., size 10 itemset) because the multiplication of probabilistic values of *expected support* becomes very small. Another limitation of probabilistic values is that, for all uncertain situations, the probability is not the best solution [23], [32], e.g., if we search a tall player for the basketball team with height 7^{ft} and there is 0.99 probability that we get the right player in California. In this case, the algorithm ignores all players having 6^{ft}11^{inches} height; even they are also tall.

Here fuzzy logic is introduced [33-35] and such data is stored as a *membership function* which is associated with each item in the database, e.g., FD in Table 1. FIM on FD can be performed by calculating *fuzzy support* on the basis of fuzzy min/max/mean operator, e.g., if fuzzy min operator is used then *fuzzy support* [36-37] of {milk, eggs} in Table 1 will be 0.24, if fuzzy max operator is used then *fuzzy support* of {milk, eggs} in Table 1 will be 2.5, if fuzzy mean operator is used then *fuzzy support* of {milk, eggs} in Table 1 will be 1.37. Many algorithms have been developed for generating frequent items from FD such as Fuzzy Transaction Data Mining Algorithm (FTDA) [16], Uncertain Data Mining (UDM)[25]. The min/max operators used by fuzzy algorithms are not able to aggregate all values while calculating *fuzzy support* and hence the generated results are not interesting. In [38], a method was developed for calculating support by using OWA operator as FAOWA. In some other cases, frequent items are calculated for the combination of both certain and uncertain databases.

In the calculation of frequent itemsets, not only the itemset occurring frequency matters but the relationship among the items is also essential. The success of a business process or a market product also depends on, how the other products are increasing or decreasing the sale of our product. The relation among two or more items in a transactional database is determined by correlation and the itemsets who qualify the user-specified correlation level is called interesting items. The correlation between items is determined by correlation coefficient, e.g. Pearson's correlation coefficient, moreover, based on the correlation coefficient, various FIM algorithms have been developed such as Directed Acyclic Graph Correlated Probabilistic Database Model (DACCPDM), Correlated Frequent Probabilistic Model(CFPM) and Fuzzy Correlated Data Mining Algorithm.

Consider two items A, B and let $\rho_A(x_i)$ is the *existential probability* of item A in the i^{th} transaction and $\rho_B(y_i)$ is the *existential probability* of item B in the i^{th} transaction. The correlation coefficient between A and B can be defined as.

$$r_{\rho(A,B)} = \frac{\rho(x_i y_i) - \rho_A(x_i) \rho_B(y_i)}{\sqrt{\rho_A(x_i)(1-\rho_A(x_i)) \rho_B(y_i)(1-\rho_B(y_i))}}$$

Here, $r_{\rho(A,B)}$ is the correlation between A and B using probability. The value of $r_{\rho(A,B)}$ will lie in [-1,1] (Pearson's correlation coefficient), so $|r_{\rho(A,B)}| \leq 1$.

In another case, Consider two fuzzy items A, B and let $\mu_A(x_i)$ is the membership function of item A in the i^{th} transaction and $\mu_B(x_i)$ is the membership function of item B in the i^{th} transaction. $\bar{\mu}_A$ and $\bar{\mu}_B$ are the fuzzy means value for item A and B respectively in the database. The correlation coefficient between A and B can be defined as [5], [22].

$$r_{fm(A,B)} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\mu_A(x_i) - \bar{\mu}_A)(\mu_B(x_i) - \bar{\mu}_B)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (\mu_A(x_i) - \bar{\mu}_A)^2 \times \sum_{i=1}^n (\mu_B(x_i) - \bar{\mu}_B)^2}} \dots \text{Eq.1}$$

Here, $r_{fm(A,B)}$ is the correlation between A and B using fuzzy means. The value of $r_{fm(A,B)}$ will lie in [-1,1] (Pearson's correlation coefficient), so $|r_{fm(A,B)}| \leq 1$.

3. Problem Definition

The problem of mining frequent items by Correlation Analysis between two items using OWA, Multiple Correlation Analysis using Fuzzy Means and Multiple Correlation Analysis using OWA can be divided into following sections.

3.1. Correlation Analysis using OWA between two items

Suppose, two fuzzy sets A and B and in Eq.1 if mean value is replaced by OWA then Correlation Coefficient between A and B using OWA denoted as $r_{OWA(A,B)}$ can be calculated by the following formula

$$r_{OWA(A,B)} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\mu_A(x_i) - OWA_A)(\mu_B(x_i) - OWA_B)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (\mu_A(x_i) - OWA_A)^2 \times \sum_{i=1}^n (\mu_B(x_i) - OWA_B)^2}} \dots \text{Eq.2}$$

Here, OWA can be calculated [28] as

$$OWA(X) = OWA(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m) = \sum_{i=1}^m w_i y_i = \sum_{i=1}^m [Q(\frac{i}{m}) - Q(\frac{i-1}{m})] y_i \dots \text{Eq.3}$$

Where y_i is the i^{th} largest value amongst x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m or values of items sorted in descending order, w is the weight value and depends upon Q (fuzzy relative quantifier [28]) and $\sum_{i=1}^m w_i = 1$.

3.2. Proof of Correlation Analysis using OWA lies between -1 and 1 or $|r_{OWA(A,B)}| \leq 1$

The OWA value for an item A can be calculated as from Eq.3.

$$OWA_A = \sum_{i=1}^m w_i \mu_A(y_i) \quad \dots \text{Eq.4}$$

and for item B as

$$OWA_B = \sum_{i=1}^m w_i \mu_B(y_i) \quad \dots \text{Eq.5}$$

Let $\mu_B(y_i) = a\mu_A(y_i) + b$, where a and b are two constants.

Therefore from Eq.5.

$$\begin{aligned} OWA_B &= \sum_{i=1}^m w_i (a\mu_A(y_i) + b) \\ OWA_B &= a \sum_{i=1}^m w_i \mu_A(y_i) + b \sum_{i=1}^m w_i \end{aligned}$$

Here $\sum_{i=1}^m w_i = 1$

So,

$$OWA_B = aOWA_A + b \quad \dots \text{Eq.6}$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_B(x_i) - OWA_B &= a\mu_A(y_i) + b - (aOWA_A + b) \\ &= a\mu_A(y_i) - aOWA_A \\ &= a(\mu_A(y_i) - OWA_A) \end{aligned} \quad \dots \text{Eq.7}$$

Put the values from Eq.7 into Eq.2 and $r_{OWA(A,B)}$ can be calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} r_{OWA(A,B)} &= \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\mu_A(x_i) - OWA_A)(\mu_B(x_i) - OWA_B)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (\mu_A(x_i) - OWA_A)^2 \times \sum_{i=1}^n (\mu_B(x_i) - OWA_B)^2}} \\ r_{OWA(A,B)} &= \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\mu_A(x_i) - OWA_A)a(\mu_A(y_i) - OWA_A)}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (\mu_A(x_i) - OWA_A)^2 \times \sum_{i=1}^n (a(\mu_A(y_i) - OWA_A))^2}} \\ r_{OWA(A,B)} &= \frac{a}{\sqrt{a^2}} = \frac{a}{|a|} = \pm 1 \end{aligned}$$

So, it can be said that $r_{OWA(A,B)}$ Always lies between -1 and 1.

3.3. Frequent Itemset Mining by Multiple Correlation Analysis using Fuzzy Means for more than two items

An itemset (l_1, l_2) is said to be frequent if its fuzzy support (fs) in the database is greater than or equal to user-specified minimum fuzzy support (mfs) and an itemset (l_1, l_2) is said to be interesting if correlation (corr) between the items is greater than or equal to user-specified minimum correlation (mcr). Therefore, the fuzzy support of an itemset can be defined as

$$fs(l_1, l_2, \dots, l_m) = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^n \min(\mu(l_1), \mu(l_2), \dots, \mu(l_m))}{n} \geq mfs \quad \dots \text{Eq.8}$$

Here n is the number of transactions in database and m is the number of items in the itemset.

The correlation coefficient $r_{l_1, l_2, l_3, \dots, l_m}$ among $l_1, l_2, l_3, \dots, l_m$ variables can be defined as

$$r_{l_1, l_2, l_3, \dots, l_m}^2 = 1 - \sum_{j_1, j_2, \dots, j_m} (\det[r(m)|j_1, j_2, \dots, j_m])^2 \quad \dots \text{Eq.9}$$

In the proposed method, variables $l_1, l_2, l_3, \dots, l_m$ are the items of FD and $r(m)$ is the value of the correlation coefficient between two items using fuzzy means. Therefore, the Correlation Coefficient by using fuzzy means among multiple variables r_{fm} can be defined as

$$r_{fm, l_1, l_2, l_3, \dots, l_m}^2 = 1 - \sum_{j_1, j_2, \dots, j_m} (\det[r_{fm}(m) | j_1, j_2, \dots, j_m])^2$$

$$r_{fm_{l_1, l_2, l_3, \dots, l_m}}^2 = 1 - \det \begin{bmatrix} r_{fm_{l_1 l_1}} & r_{fm_{l_1 l_2}} & \dots & r_{fm_{l_1 l_m}} \\ r_{fm_{l_2 l_1}} & r_{fm_{l_2 l_2}} & \dots & r_{fm_{l_2 l_m}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ r_{fm_{l_m l_1}} & r_{fm_{l_m l_2}} & \dots & r_{fm_{l_m l_m}} \end{bmatrix} \dots \text{Eq.10}$$

Therefore, an itemset is said to be frequent if $fs(l_1, l_2, \dots, l_n) \geq mfs$ and interesting if $r_{fm_{l_1, l_2, l_3, \dots, l_m}}^2 \geq mcr$.

3.4. Multiple Correlation Analysis using OWA for more than two items

In this case, the Correlation Coefficient using OWA for multiple variables or r_{owa} can be calculated by replacing r_{fm} in Eq.10 by r_{owa} and can be defined as

$$r_{owa_{l_1, l_2, l_3, \dots, l_m}}^2 = 1 - \sum_{j_1 j_2 < \dots < j_m} (\det [r_{owa(m)} \vee j_1, j_2, \dots, j_m])^2$$

$$r_{owa_{l_1, l_2, l_3, \dots, l_m}}^2 = 1 - \det \begin{bmatrix} r_{owa_{l_1 l_1}} & r_{owa_{l_1 l_2}} & \dots & r_{owa_{l_1 l_m}} \\ r_{owa_{l_2 l_1}} & r_{owa_{l_2 l_2}} & \dots & r_{owa_{l_2 l_m}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ r_{owa_{l_m l_1}} & r_{owa_{l_m l_2}} & \dots & r_{owa_{l_m l_m}} \end{bmatrix} \dots \text{Eq.11}$$

Therefore, an itemset is said to be frequent if $fs(l_1, l_2, \dots, l_m) \geq mfs$ and interesting if $r_{owa_{l_1, l_2, l_3, \dots, l_m}}^2 \geq mcr$.

3.5. Proof: OWA is a better approach than using Fuzzy Means while calculating Correlation among two or more items.

Let us assume that $X_s = \{x_{l_1}, x_{l_2}, x_{l_3} \dots \dots, x_{l_s}\}$ is the set of unexpected large values in FUDB and X_{s_A} and X_{s_B} are the sets of large values of items A and B respectively. In this case

$$\bar{\mu}_A = \frac{x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + \dots + x_n}{n} \approx \frac{x_{l_1} + x_{l_2} + x_{l_3} + \dots + x_{l_s}}{n} \approx \bar{X}_{s_A}$$

Similarly,

$$\bar{\mu}_B \approx \bar{X}_{s_B}$$

Therefore, by assigning the values of $\bar{\mu}_A$ and $\bar{\mu}_B$ into Eq.1, Correlation Coefficient can be given as,

$$r_{fm_{(A,B)}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\mu_A(x_i) - \bar{X}_{s_A})(\mu_B(x_i) - \bar{X}_{s_B})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (\mu_A(x_i) - \bar{X}_{s_A})^2 \times \sum_{i=1}^n (\mu_B(x_i) - \bar{X}_{s_B})^2}}$$

$$= \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{n-s} (\mu_A(x_i) - \bar{X}_{s_A})(\mu_B(x_i) - \bar{X}_{s_B}) + \sum_{i=1}^s (\mu_A(x_{l_s}) - \bar{X}_{s_A})(\mu_B(x_{l_s}) - \bar{X}_{s_B})}{\sqrt{(\sum_{i=1}^{n-s} (\mu_A(x_i) - \bar{X}_{s_A})^2 + \sum_{i=1}^s (\mu_A(x_{l_s}) - \bar{X}_{s_A})^2) \times ((\sum_{i=1}^{n-s} (\mu_B(x_i) - \bar{X}_{s_B})^2 + \sum_{i=1}^s (\mu_B(x_{l_s}) - \bar{X}_{s_B})^2))}}$$

$$r_{fm_{(A,B)}} = \frac{(n-s)\bar{X}_{s_A}\bar{X}_{s_B} + \sum_{i=1}^s (\mu_A(x_{l_s}) - \bar{X}_{s_A})(\mu_B(x_{l_s}) - \bar{X}_{s_B})}{\sqrt{((n-s)\bar{X}_{s_A}^2 + \sum_{i=1}^s (\mu_A(x_{l_s}) - \bar{X}_{s_A})^2) \times ((n-s)\bar{X}_{s_B}^2 + \sum_{i=1}^s (\mu_B(x_{l_s}) - \bar{X}_{s_B})^2)}} [\because \forall x_{l_s} \gg \forall x_i] \dots \text{Eq.12}$$

From Eq.12 it is clear that $r_{fm_{(A,B)}}$ can be determined by the values of X_{s_A} and X_{s_B} .

In another case, from Eq.4

$$OWA_A = \sum_{i=1}^m w_i \mu_A(y_i)$$

Here y is the set of values of an item in descending order. Therefore,

$$OWA_A = \sum_{i=1}^s w_i \mu_A(y_i) OWA_A + \sum_{i=s+1}^m w_i \mu_A(y_i) [\because X_s \text{ is the set of large values}]$$

In Eq.3 relative quantifier $Q(r)$ can be calculated as [28]

$$Q(r) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } r < a \\ \frac{r-a}{b-a} & \text{if } a \leq r \leq b \\ 1 & \text{if } r > b \end{cases}$$

Therefore,

If $s < a$

Then $\sum_{i=1}^s w_i \mu_A(y_i) = 0$

and,

$$OWA_A = \sum_{i=s+1}^m w_i \mu_A(y_i) \quad \dots \text{Eq.13}$$

Similarly,

$$OWA_B = \sum_{i=s+1}^m w_i \mu_B(y_i) \quad \dots \text{Eq.14}$$

Hence, from Eq.13 and Eq.14, it is clear that the calculation of OWA value for A and B does not include the values higher than s or exclude the higher values. Consequently, the value of $r_{OWA(A,B)}$ does not contain the impact of high values. Therefore, if the database contains some high values the $r_{OWA(A,B)}$ consider the majority values and shows more interesting association or the value of $r_{OWA(A,B)}$ is more interesting as compared to $r_{fm(A,B)}$.

4. Algorithms

In this paper, two algorithms are presented as *Multiple Correlation Analysis using Fuzzy Means (MCAFM)* and *Multiple Correlation Analysis using Ordered Weighted Averaging (MCAOWA)* as follows:

4.1. Multiple Correlation Analysis using Fuzzy Means (MCAFM)

Input: Z (A fuzzy uncertain transactional database), mfs (minimum fuzzy support) and, mcr (minimum correlation); Output: S (frequent and interesting itemsets in Z)

MCAFM Algorithm

- (1) $S_1 = \text{Size_1_frequent_items}(Z)$; // for each size_1 item $fs \geq mfs$
- (2) for ($i = 2$; $S_{i-1} \neq \emptyset$; $i++$) {
- (3) $X_i = \text{candid_gen}(S_{i-1})$; // Generate candidates, join, prun
- (4) for each row $t \in Z$ { // scan database
- (5) $X_i = \text{subset}(X_i, t)$; // get all candidates
- (6) for each item $x \in X_i$

- (7) $fs(x) = \min(\mu(l1), \mu(l2), \dots, \mu(lm))$
- (8) $x.fs = x.fs + fs(x)$
- (9) }
- (10) $x.fs = x.fs / |Z|$
- (11) if $(x.fs \geq mfs)$ then {
- (12) $r_{fm_x}^2 = 1 - \sum_{j_1, j_2 < \dots, j_m} (det [r_{fm(m)} \vee j_1, j_2, \dots, j_m])^2$
- (13) $S_i = \{x \in X_i \mid r_{fm_x}^2 \geq mcr\}$
- (14) }
- (15) return $S = \cup_i S_i$;

4.2. MCAOWA (Multiple Correlation Analysis using Ordered Weighted Averaging)

Input: Z (A fuzzy uncertain transactional database), mfs (minimum fuzzy support) and, mcr (minimum correlation); Output: S (frequent and interesting itemsets in Z)

MCAOWA Algorithm

- (1) $S_i = \text{Size_1_frequent_items}(Z)$; // for each size_1 item $fs \geq mfs$
- (2) for $(i = 2; S_{i-1} \neq \emptyset; i++)$ {
- (3) $X_i = \text{candid_gen}(S_{i-1})$; // Generate candidates, join, prun
- (4) for each row $t \in Z$ { // scandatabase
- (5) $X_i = \text{subset}(X_i, t)$; // get all candidates
- (6) for each item $x \in X_i$:
- (7) $fs(x) = \min(\mu(l1), \mu(l2), \dots, \mu(lm))$
- (8) $x.fs = x.fs + fs(x)$
- (9) }
- (10) $x.fs = x.fs / |Z|$
- (11) if $(x.fs \geq mfs)$ then {
- (12) $r_{OWA_{a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots, a_m}}^2 = 1 - \sum_{j_1, j_2 < \dots, j_m} (det [r_{OWA(m)} \vee j_1, j_2, \dots, j_m])^2$
- (13) $S_i = \{x \in X_i \mid r_{fm_x}^2 \geq mcr\}$
- (14) }
- (15) return $S = \cup_i S_i$;

In the above algorithms, a fuzzy uncertain transactional database is given as input and for calculating frequent as well as interesting itemsets, *minimum fuzzy support* and *minimum correlation* level is provided by the user as input. Both algorithms follow the Apriori pattern of execution. In line-1 size_1 frequent items calculated on the basis of *fuzzy support* only because for calculating correlation at least two items required. Thereafter line-2 to 14 executed repeatedly until all results are calculated. In line-3, function `candid_gen()` is used to generate all candidates by joining the frequent items from the previous stage and pruning them. These candidate itemsets scanned in the database to calculate *fuzzy support*. In line-11, candidates who qualify user given *minimum fuzzy support* are checked and called frequent items. In line-12, the correlation coefficient is calculated only among the items of frequent itemset from line-11 using fuzzy means or OWA and the itemsets who qualify minimum correlation are then added to final set S in line-13. In line-15 all size frequent and interesting items are combined.

5. An Example to demonstrate the work.

Consider Table.3 and Table.4, let minimum support¹ =0.05 and *mcr*=0.25. In Table.3 an uncertain transactional database is given and in Table.3 frequent and interesting items are calculated.

Table 3. Example of an Uncertain Database

TID	Items				
	1	2	3	4	5
1	0.9	0.02	0.25	0.03	0.3
2	0.18	0.03	0.15	0.01	0.1
3	0.16	0.9	0.17	0.2	0.01
4	0.8	0.09	0.03	0.3	0.8
5	0.04	0.12	0.05	0.14	0.01
6	0.06	0.8	0.08	0.13	0.19
7	0.08	0.15	0.04	0.17	0.9
8	0.1	0.02	0.01	0.05	0.18
9	0.01	0.04	0.03	0.06	0.12
10	0.03	0.3	0.14	0.09	0.08

Table 4. Frequent Itemsets generation by MCAFM, MCAOWA and CFPM

C ₁	F _s	L ₁	C ₂	F _s	P _s	Corr FM	Corr OWA	CFPM	L ₂ FM	L ₂ OWA	L ₂ Prob	C ₃ FM	C ₃ OWA	f _s	Corr OWA
1	0.236	1	12	0.054	0.03156	-0.273915242	-0.088318858						145	0.059	0.68718
2	0.247	2	13	0.078	0.03187	0.405975682	0.437441827		13	13					
3	0.095	3	14	0.077	0.03361	0.218598224	0.251249381			14					
4	0.118	4	15	0.15	0.1035	0.423753025	0.498402617	0.212518	15	15	15				
5	0.269	5	23	0.06	0.02846	0.214085306	0.261895037			23					
			24	0.087	0.03846	0.352527307	0.373624624		24	24					
			25	0.064	0.04106	-0.268166943	-0.110367015								
			34	0.054	0.00911	-0.33324166	-0.301361875								
			35	0.064	0.0184	-0.316924194	-0.234251109								
			45	0.085	0.04545	0.536197786	0.54518274		45	45					

Table Abbreviations:

C₁:- size-1 candidates, L₁:- size-1 frequent items, f_s:- fuzzy support, p_s:- probabilistic support

CorrFM:- Correlation using Fuzzy Means, CorrOWA:- Correlation using OWA, CFPM:- Correlated Frequent Probabilistic Model

L₂FM:- size-2 frequent and interesting items calculated by using fuzzy means, L₂OWA:-size-2 frequent and interesting items calculated by using OWA, L₂Prob:-size-2 frequent and interesting items calculated by using Probability

If the given database is considered as Probabilistic Uncertain Database then minimum support can be called as minimum probabilistic support mps and If the given database is considered as Fuzzy Uncertain Database then minimum support can be called as minimum fuzzy support mfs

C_3FM :- size-3 candidate generated by size-2 frequent items using Fuzzy Means, C_3OWA :- size-3 candidate generated by size-2 frequent items using OWA.

In the above example frequent and interesting items are calculated using proposed MCAFM and MCAOWA methods and compared with CFPM method.

In Table.3, mfs or mps is 0.05. Therefore, all C_1 qualifies for L_1 in all three cases (i.e., MCAFM, MCAOWA and CFPM). Later, L_1 are combined to form C_2 and correlation using fuzzy means, OWA and probability is calculated for candidates who qualify mfs or mps . In this database (Table.2) the following points can be noted.

- The database contains a total of 50 values in the following ranges

Range	Number of values
0.0-0.2	40
0.21-0.3	4
0.71-0.9	6

- In this database most of the values belong to a lower range, that's why a number of frequent items calculated by MCAOWA are larger than MCAFM (i.e., 12 in MCAOWA and 9 in MCAFM).
- MCAOWA calculates the correlation between the 44 lower values and ignores the 6 higher values on the other hand MCAFM consider all values, so the impact of 6 higher values is greater.
- Due to multiplication of probabilistic values the association rules loss is very high in CFPM. Therefore, this method is less efficient to calculate frequent items compare to MCAOWA and MCAFM.
- It can be said that MCAOWA computes more interesting correlation compare to MCAFM and CFPM.

6. Results Comparison

In the following section, the comparison of results is discussed by executing MCAFM, MCAOWA and CFPM on three standard available real life datasets (i.e. Gazelle, Connect and mushroom)[25, 38] as UDB. The programs of *Correlation analysis* have been coded in C and executed on Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-5200U 2.2GHz processor, using 4GB of RAM and Ubuntu-15.10-desktop-amd64. The results can be discussed in the following sections

6.1. Gazelle Dataset

In this dataset, there is a total of 59602 transactions and 497 items.

Figure 1. Correlation Analysis using MCAFM, MCAOWA and CFPM on Gazelle dataset
 The values inside this dataset belong to the following range.

Range	Percentage of values
0.0-0.09	0.05%
0.7-0.79	0.0008%
0.8-0.89	13.6%
0.9-1.0	81.5%

Therefore, it can be said that in this dataset most of the values of items having a membership function greater than 0.9. Consequently, the correlation coefficient calculated by MCAFM as given in Figure.1 is between 0.9-1.0. In other words, it can be said that in this dataset most of the items from 497 items are highly correlated to each other, which is practically not possible. CFPM gives a smaller number of frequent items compare to MCAFM but with almost same correlation as in MCAFM. In Figure.1, correlation calculated by MCOWA is also presented which reflects some true picture of association among items because at this point the impact of high values is removed then the correlation is calculated among items. In other words, MCOWA is useful to calculate interestingness among low values, which is ignored by MCAFM and CFPM.

6.2. Connect Dataset

In this dataset, there is a total of 67557 transactions and 130 items.

The values inside this dataset belong to the following range.

Range	Percentage of values
0.6-0.69	0.000016%
0.7-0.79	0.02%
0.8-0.89	48.5%
0.9-1.0	49.5%

Figure 2. Correlation Analysis using MCAFM, MCAOWA CFPM on Connect dataset

In this dataset number of transactions are higher, and a number of items are smaller compared to Gazelle dataset, or it can be said that the size of each transaction is smaller compare to the previous dataset. In this dataset, all values are from higher range, i.e. 0.8-1.0, and for calculating w (Eq.3) the value of Q is determined for $a=0.2$ and $b=0.8$ or in other words, all values larger than 0.8 are removed. Here, MCAOWA is applied only on a few values and correlation between them is depicted in Figure.2. Therefore, the lower values from 0.6-0.8 are observed by MCAOWA and correlation is calculated among them. On the other hand, MCAFM and CFPM operated only for high values.

6.3. Mushroom Dataset

In this dataset, there is a total of 8124 transactions and 119 items.

Figure 3. Correlation Analysis using MCAFM, MCAOWA CFPM on

The values inside this dataset belong to the following range.

Range	Percentage of values
0.01-0.09	8.96%
0.1-0.19	9.99%
0.2-0.29	9.96%
0.3-0.39	9.98%
0.4-0.49	10.14%
0.5-0.59	10.11%
0.6-0.69	10.01%
0.7-0.79	10.25%
0.8-0.89	10.02%
0.9-1.0	10.57%

This dataset is totally different from previous two and all values are distributed equally. In such type of dataset, it cannot be said that high values or low values have more importance. So, in this case removing the effect of high value is not a good idea. In Figure 3, it can be seen that the results calculated by MCAFM are more interesting compare to CFPM and MCAOWA. CFPM gives less number of frequent items because of multiplication of probabilities high size frequent items cannot be calculated.

7. Conclusion and future direction

Correlation analysis is a fundamental technique for analyzing daily life situations, e.g., if two persons meet for some business but unknown to each other at that time correlation between them may not strong. However, if they meet in the presence of any third person, known to both of them, then correlation among these three become stronger. In this paper, a new technique is used to analyze large dataset and by finding out the more interesting association. The performance of MCAOWA is better compared to MCAFM and CFPM when implemented on such a database, where some very high or very low values affecting the performance of *correlation analysis* (experiments 6.1 and 6.2). In another case, if datasets contain values which are distributed equally (experiment 6.3) in dataset MCAFM performs better than MCAOWA and CFPM.

Further, in future, a neutrosophy logic[39] can be incorporated. The various application of neutrosophy logic from data mining and artificial intelligence perspective in several applications have been reported in.

In addition, it would be interesting to explore how correlation coefficient of neutrosophic set[40] (CCNS) shall behave? This paper exploits fuzzy based correlation, moving forward we need to assess the neutrosophic related correlation performance for the related problems. Like, correlation coefficients of interval valued neutrosophic set (CCINS) and CCNS. Since it is worth to mention that CCNS has the positive, negative and neutral correlation as it is the case with statistical spearman correlation and so forth. Thus, in this context knowing its behavior and performance would be challenging and may open new research dimensions to the related field of study.

Figure 4. Neutrosophy based pattern mining

We have outlined an approach to incorporate the neutrosophy for the above purpose. The detail approach is shown in figure 4. It is envisaged that the approach can open new dimensions in the field of neutrosophy and data mining.

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